

Mathematics for multispecies' flourishing

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Why teach mathematics? We introduce an ethical framework for teaching elementary mathematics, “Mathematics for Multispecies’ Flourishing” (M4MSF). We draw upon Su, who has promoted the idea of doing mathematics as a route to human flourishing, and Seligman’s PERMA theory of well-being. We frame M4MSF as connecting content to needs for survival, transcendence, belonging, dignity and challenge through considerations of land, language, lore (story), living, logic and learning. This framing extends ethnomathematical and culturally responsive approaches to mathematics and grounds our understanding of multispecies’ flourishing as a right of all species. We present examples from a completed project with pre-service elementary teachers in Canada.

Conceptions of human flourishing are emerging as a focus in research on human well-being (eg., Seligman, 2011), teacher education (eg., Cherkowski & Walker, 2018) and mathematics education (eg., Su, 2020). In our opinion these frameworks while useful continue to privilege a specific anthropo/eco/ego/homo-cidal genre of being human (Wynter, 2015) as a bio-cultural exceptional species (Haraway in Mitman, 2019) and place human interest — including the interest of ahuman capital (MacCormack, 2020) — above all else. We recognise however that there is not and has never been human flourishing at community and population levels without — or that is independent of — multispecies’ flourishing (Brink, 2008), and, at present, in many places, the multispecies world is far from flourishing.

Our thesis then is that current conceptualizations of a “Mathematics for Human Flourishing” (Su, 2020), or “Rehumanizing mathematics” (e.g., Goffney & Gutiérrez, 2018; Tan et al., 2019) while welcome, necessary, and important contributions to ongoing conversations in our fields and for practice, continue in a tradition of an anthropocentric mathematics education that fails to attend to the evidence that there has never existed widespread human flourishing anywhere without simultaneous attention to multispecies flourishing (the flourishing of a multiplicity of biological and other forms) and multispecies’ flourishing (the right of other species to flourish). Our shift in thinking and argument in this paper is to invite readers into a mythopoetic re-framing of what would traditionally be rendered within ethnomathematical or culturally relevant frames.

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From human flourishing to multispecies flourishing to multispecies' flourishing

Kirksey and Helmreich (2010) describe the emergence of multispecies ethnography describing it as centering on, “how a multitude of organisms’ livelihoods shape and are shaped by political, economic and cultural forces” (p. 545). van Dooren, Kirksey and Munster (2016) use the concept of “passionate immersion” as a frame for multispecies studies that unsettles notions of species, opening up ways of knowing and understanding others and has implications for epistemology, political philosophy and ethics around questions of, “liv[ing] with others in entangled worlds of contingency and uncertainty [...] [and] inhabiting and co-constituting worlds well” (p. 1). This “species turn” in anthropology has spilled over into other social sciences (such as education, especially early years education (see for example the common worlds project, n.d.; Taylor & Pacini-Ketchabaw, 2018) (and has a much longer history in the humanities and arts) as well as beginning to influence Scientific practice.

According to van Dooren et al (2016)

a multispecies approach focuses on the multitudes of lively agents that bring one another into being through entangled relations that include, but always also exceed, dynamics of predator and prey, parasite and host, researcher and researched, symbiotic partner, or indifferent neighbor. But these larger contexts are not mere environments in the sense of a homogeneous, static background for a focal subject. Rather, they are *complex “ecologies of selves,” dynamic milieus that are continually shaped and reshaped, actively – even if not always knowingly – crafted through the sharing of “meanings, interests and affects,” as well as flesh, minerals, fluids, genetic materials, and much more...this multiplicity, this multiplying of perspectives and influences, is key to what multispecies studies is all about (pp. 3-4, italics added).*

In short, multispecies work is a study in complexity of living, learning and becoming with, alongside and through other planetary beings and cosmological phenomena. Khan (2020) begins to develop the first aspects of the framework of a mathematics for multispecies' flourishing. Framed mythopoetically it puts into conversation the complex assemblage of Sylvia Wynter's formulation of Man and the ceremony found or second emergence of an autopoiesis of the human with that of multispecies' scholars such as Donna Haraway and her notions of making kin. Speculatively, Khan (2020) offers that a mathematics education for multispecies' flourishing might find a first analogy, “in enactivism's focus on structural coupling among individuals and their environment and extend this to include indigenous wisdom sensibilities/ spiritualities, which do not view the multispecies world through plantation logics and economics as ‘resources’ to be exploited and profited from but as ‘kin’ and ‘nations’ to be partnered with in teaching, learning, living, and dying well.”

We offer that a Mathematics For Multispecies' Flourishing acknowledges and seeks to address the needs of some specific member(s) of the multispecies world for survival, transcendence, belonging, dignity and challenge. We attempted to illustrate as well that our notion is of a set of reciprocal relations among these elements, i.e., none is more important, all are necessary though in certain periods one may become a priority, e.g., survival. We note some similarity to Maslow's hierarchy/pyramid of needs but think our non-hierarchical

relational framing offers something different in its visual metaphor and the commitments entailed. The second part of the image identifies what we believe one must attend to in doing mathematics for multispecies' flourishing. In this first iteration we identify relationships with land, the languages that are spoken by humans and other species, the stories (lore) told about that land through those languages that enable a continuity of living forms over time, the logics (grammars and biosemiotic codes) that structure relationships of meaning from which learning emerges across different embodied complex systems ranging from the subcellular to the mytho-cosmological.

Figure 1: The frame of multispecies flourishing as a connection with course content.

In our meetings together we also discussed framing aspects as flourishing promoting, flourishing limiting, and anti-flourishing. Without getting into a full discussion here, we point to poverty, educational inequality, colonialism, racism, traumas, and pandemics as examples of flourishing-limiting situations in humans. We place, during the period of their expression, genocide (including species extinction), fascism, the coloniality of power and murder as anti-flourishing. We also found that across cultures, geographies and times, communal activities such as games, group hunting/agriculture/shelter construction, ceremonies and rituals, together with art/craft/making practices contributed to survival, transcendence, belonging, dignity and challenge while always being situated in certain places, with multiple overlapping multispecies languages, telling polysemous stories and allowing plural logics and ways of sense-making. These communal activities we often found framed within a respect and deep care for the multispecies world and they became multiple sources of inspiration and exemplification. We also discussed the model and logic and ethics of the plantation as a powerful contributor to flourishing-limiting practices and anti-flourishing events.

It is our belief that pursuing a mathematics for flourishing or a mathematics for multispecies flourishing requires attending to the life-histories of individuals, not as social workers, but as compassionate human beings interested in the flourishing of all learners and not just those of human beings. We suggest that a mathematics for multispecies' flourishing

steps further than the concerns of the mathematics proficiency framework and the anthropocentrism of most forms of ethnomathematics research by keeping foregrounded the 5 inter-related needs of survival, transcendence, dignity, belonging and challenge that necessarily require developing meaningful relationships with lands, languages, lores, living, logics through which one curates one's learning alongside multispecies others to whom one has responsibilities.

Research context

In the context of our work with pre-service elementary teachers we have used the provocation offered by Cherkowski and Walker (2018) below with teachers and ourselves,

What if you were to imagine that your primary role as an educator is to learn how to thrive in your role, and, in so doing, *to continually co-explore and to enthusiastically facilitate all means by which each person in your learning community flourishes along with you* most of the time? (Cherkowski & Walker, 2018, italics added)

The provocation provided the impetus for the design of EDEL 415, Issues in Elementary Mathematics Education: Mathematics Education for Multispecies Flourishing which I (Steven) taught in the Winter term of 2020 (Jan.–April). The specific focus of the Section was identified as “Mathematics Education for Multispecies Flourishing” and offered participants opportunities to examine issues that affect mathematics education whilst continuing to develop their knowledge and skills in mathematics content knowledge and knowledge for teaching. In my outline I noted,

We shall inquire into necessary conditions for promoting multispecies flourishing through mathematics education during the elementary grades. Consequently, some aspects of the content and discussions in this course may be unsettling, controversial, or emotionally and intellectually challenging. The instructor will do his best to make the learning spaces places of loving kindness where the students are able to critically, compassionately and thoughtfully engage with difficult content.

The course had an enrolment of 32 students and meet weekly for 3 hours. We were forced to move to emergency remote teaching in mid-March as a result of COVID-19 lockdowns and ended the course in this mode of engagement. This made the concerns of the course especially those of survival, transcendence, dignity, belonging and challenge and the places and paces of learning even more salient.

During our in-person meetings we explored a variety of mathematical activities. Hang opened one session with a presentation about one aspect related to the Lunar New Year celebration in Vietnam - a story of making Bánh Chưng. The presentation over time provided one of the concrete examples of a mathematics for multispecies' flourishing and lived alongside others such as understanding communal buffalo hunting on the North American plains, building paper fractal snowflakes, solids and shadows, appreciating Indigenous games and methods for measuring, and making kolam sand drawings. Importantly, it provided an early hub to which to refer back to as students' and our own understandings of what a mathematics for multispecies' flourishing might be about.

The data comes from weekly student mathcuration journals and reflexive conversations of the instructional/research team throughout the planning, delivery and post-course analysis.

Student responses to sessions

Through the presentation and discussion students became aware of several mathematical ideas related to the preparation of the cakes and the relevance of working to connect subject matter to learners' cultures and contexts. Students related the content of Hang's shared story to specific mathematical content in the programme of studies including estimation, symmetry and measurement. Some students made the connection that although this was a singular example it could be generalised to other cultural practices, i.e. that one could connect mathematics meaningfully and respectfully to aspects of learners' cultural backgrounds or bring one's own culture into the classroom. We find evidence for this for example in the following excerpts from several students:

Something I understood today, was that *we can take situations that are not explicitly related to math and connect it to the subject...*When taking in [the guest speaker's] presentation from the stance of a teacher, I was able to view the relationships to math and it made math more meaningful. *She used math concepts like symmetry, estimating and measurement without explicitly teaching about them.* This presentation mattered, because in my future teaching I can try and use this to connect different students' cultures into my lessons.

While I myself celebrate this holiday, *I have never considered it from a mathematical standpoint before.* It was interesting to learn about the ways mathematics is embedded into our everyday lives, especially within our culture. I think teachers have always struggled in finding out how to make math meaningful to their students, and I think this is a good strategy for doing so. As [R] said in class, a great extension task would be to have students find how math is present in their own cultures and practices.

Not only would students be able to learn about another culture in a hands-on way, but they'd also be *able to incorporate mathematics (such as through finding perimeter, area, etc.).* It could be used as a nice Social Studies connection as well...making these Lunar cakes involves a variety of mathematical concepts. It is *something that requires actual understanding of math, not memorization.* I do think that education needs to move in this direction on this topic, and I believe we are slowly starting to see this trend.

Deep connections and relationships were conceptualized between the different perspectives thus showcasing the underpinning philosophies of making kin and multispecies flourishing *with* and *in* mathematics. The above quotation also showcases the dynamic and continuous shifting and developing of pedagogical beliefs that enables students to curate their mathematical and professional identities.

Students began to see the teaching and learning of mathematics as a plurality of cultural contexts and cross-curricular framings. In other words, students began to see the teaching and learning of mathematics, and school mathematics, as a culturally situated phenomena that spans multiple subjects and lifeworlds. This shift inherently provides a more rich and complex mathematical learning story to occur.

Bringing the ‘real’ world, life-worlds of students into mathematics was one aspect that pre-service teachers identified and valued prior to the course. On more than one occasion, students expressed their developing beliefs/values about the importance of connecting content to the life-worlds of students. This activity explicitly framed within a perspective of multispecies’ flourishing, enabled students to ‘see’ and ‘open’ a route to engaging students beyond eurocentric/western curricular content by strengthening this connection between familial curriculum making and the Programme of Studies’ learning outcomes.

In the quote below from another pre-service teacher we observe a valuing of language and aspects of culture. They also articulate clear connections to the ideas of flourishing and survival as well as explicit naming of “belonging” appropriate to this point in the course. In the excerpt we also see a possible value of making mathematics a place that is like a home for learners.

Passing down language, celebrations, values, religion, and also games is an integral part of cultural flourishing and survival. Creating belonging, especially in a new homeland, is extremely important. Without belonging, there would be no “home”.

In envisioning such a home - through mathematics education classroom practice - there is a recognition of the value of community formation and collective if not communal activity. Another writes,

Collaborating with parents and community members in classroom activities would be a benefit to everyone as well. It would be interesting to see how students could connect with each other and the community, as well as think deeper about how their own traditions can be connected to subjects like mathematics (as in Tran’s precision in creating her Chung cakes).

This looking forward (in time) and outward (to the community) is not framed within the typical discourse of the community as a resource or containing resources to be exploited for learning but the community as a true *partner*, a collaborator, in teaching and learning (mathematics). This is emerging as a critical theme as schools re-open.

What conceptions of mathematics for multispecies flourishing are developed?

Earlier we presented our explicit framework for thinking about a mathematics for multispecies’ flourishing. This is more intentionally and fully developed than the one initially presented to the pre-service teachers. We acknowledge that the students’ reflections on the nascent concept have shaped and contributed to this developing idea.

Through the experience of Hang’s presentation, students not only began to attend to the cultural and language aspects of students’ lifeworlds, they also began to interpret and develop their own conceptualizations of Mathematics for Multispecies Flourishing. In fact, students learned about a variety of different aspects of multispecies flourishing (and related philosophies) which act to open opportunities for possible futures, and strengthen their existing teacher identities (Garner & Kaplan, 2019).

Students appeared to have pre-existing teaching philosophies that value connecting mathematics to everyday life and practice. Through this activity they were invited and welcomed to see more concretely how that philosophy could be enacted. We find evidence for this in the following student notes:

Although on the surface it may seem as if they are just “something you always do”, there is always a rich meaning and sentiment behind every ritual. In this case, this Lunar New Year ritual is a way of connecting people to both multiple places and multiple people.

In these last sentences for example, we see students as expressing a value for “respect” and “deep understanding” (dignity), connecting it to “tradition” (belonging) through story (language and lore) within the Canadian context of ongoing multiculturalism where many parents are “raising children in a new home country” (land). We also note in the reflection (and from in-class conversations) that collaboration with parents and communities is expressed as part of their imagined future practice (and identity) as teachers of mathematics in the elementary grades (dignity and belonging).

The presentation was described as “memorable” and featured in the curated reflection on the session of many students. One student noted in their curations journal after this third session the difficulty or rather challenge of making sense of this concept of Multispecies Flourishing. However, a specific example allowed for connections to be made to the elements of the framework. They wrote,

Trying to grasp *Mathematics Education for Multispecies Flourishing* has been difficult. It is so far from anything that I have ever known about math that the journey has been a bit rocky. It was enlightening in today's class to see the separate ways that math can allow a species to flourish. Looking at the example of the New Years cake from Vietnam, we can see multispecies flourishing *through survival, transcendence, dignity, belonging and challenge*.

Though this student did not elaborate on these connections, others did, for example another wrote,

Making the cake brings up several connections [for me] for example: Survival- *of the culture*, food, water. Dignity- *sense of identity* related to accomplishment, the idea of *belonging* to a culture and family... Making a connection to *where all the materials are from*...Extend and challenge students to *see how math is present in their own lives. Thinking long term, timing, situation of practice, when will this be appropriate*, New year? Or could you build it off traditions. You have to think *across discipline*. (italics added)

Others more quickly made connections to the framework on flourishing and multispecies flourishing which had been presented in the previous session one week earlier.

This tradition incorporates many elements, including survival (food is needed for human survival), transcendence (cake links to ancestors, the homeland, and any absent members of the culture), and dignity (learning to care for the leaves used to make the cake, and discovering a sense of identity [belonging] and accomplishment [challenge] after successfully making them).

For other students the connection was not to “multispecies flourishing” but to “multicultural flourishing” which is in itself a small but noteworthy elaboration of the

frameworks of culturally responsive mathematics (Nicols et al., 2020), ethnomathematics (Stathopoulou & Appelbaum, 2016) and mathematics for human flourishing (Su, 2020). Several noted that such activities could not only contribute to deeper awareness but deeper conceptual understanding of mathematics,

My goal when I get into the classroom is to have students understand math in a way that not only makes them feel comfortable with the subject, but also so that they can use mathematics in the real world to solve problems. For example, making these Lunar cakes involves a variety of mathematical concepts [...] It is something that requires actual understanding of math, not memorization.

Repeatedly the pre-service teachers told us during the course that the concept of multispecies flourishing was new to them and found it difficult to make sense of it. This difficulty with a novel concept and framework was anticipated. We offered over the duration of the course multiple experiences and instantiations, with intentional and strategic variation, to make sense of the concept. For example, within the first half of the course I heard, “I’m struggling to understand how I can specifically incorporate multispecies flourishing in my classroom and lessons. I think because it is such a vague concept, it is hard to concretely apply it.” In this I read the familiar press for immediate application prior to deep, connected understanding and the need for concrete examples. A specific learning strategy employed in the course however was the inter-leaving (reference) and recursive elaboration (Davis & Simmt, 2003) of examples across sessions. Hang’s presentation represented an early example that was serendipitous but allowed for the concrete connections to begin to be made.

As the course instructor when I initially proposed the idea of mathematics for multispecies flourishing (M4MSF) as the theme I had a not quite fully formed idea of what it could mean (but an intuition that there was something there of value to teachers and myself). The elements of survival, transcendence, dignity, belonging and challenge were already present from my reading of Brink’s (2008) study of Head Smashed In buffalo jump and other scholarship (see Khan, 2020). At the start of the course I was definitely thinking in terms not of multispecies’ flourishing but of multispecies flourishing. Distinguishing between these two has been important for me in recognising the difference that each signals. The latter is about plurality, i.e. the ability of all species to flourish. The former is about *the right* of all species to be able pursue flourishing as an end. The pre-service teachers’ ongoing struggles with the concept and providing suitable exemplification helped me to refine this distinction and by the end of the course I had shifted to using multispecies’ flourishing in my thinking and writing.

Another learning from this example is the clear demonstration of the relationship and need for deep engagement, “passionate immersion” with the multispecies world. As we talk about what might be needed to do this work I find the traditional framings in mathematics education lesson plans as “materials” or “necessary *resources*” to be problematic and potentially exploitative. The bamboo, banana leaves, rice, beans, meat, the stories, even the plastic used to wrap the cakes are more lovingly framed as ‘partners’ in our learning to live well and not

just 'resources' to be consumed. There is a necessary recognition of the significance of relationships of interdependence and inter-vulnerability, of responsibility, care, compassion and ethics in this work.

One worry for me is just how easy it is for this still gestating concept of multispecies' flourishing to be consumed/subsumed (the mental image is phagocytosis) by other, already existing and related discourses such as ethnomathematics, culturally relevant pedagogy, rehumanizing mathematics education, mathematics for sustainability and mathematics for social justice as members of our field jostle to exploit the possibilities of their niche by colonizing other emerging discourses rather than starting with the pursuit of connection, collaboration and communal responsibilities. A mathematics for multispecies' flourishing acknowledges the debt owed to these important familial 'relatives' in providing a history and tradition of looking towards more meaningful ends for mathematics than mathematical proficiency and a less anthropocentric focus than ethnomathematics. Its specific contribution though is to attempt to de-center the privileged position of the human (and human economies and logics) as the sole benefactor in our considerations of *who* mathematics is for, with whom mathematics is done in the world, and what mathematics does *to* the world through human action and inaction. Beyond this paper what a mathematics for multispecies flourishing might look, sound, smell, taste, feel like and yet become is left to all of us, as an exercise of communal study, respectful partnerships, research, and praxis.

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